

LAZER QURILMASI YORDAMIDA TEKISLANGAN YERLARDA G'O'ZANING O'SIB RIVOJLANISHI VA HOSILDORLIGIGA TA'SIRI

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ABSTRACT

Maqolada lezerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan yerlarda go'zani o'sib-rivojlanishi va hosildorligi bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar natijalari keltirilgan bo'lib, lazerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan maydonda tuproqning sug'orish oldi namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 70-80-65 % bo'lganda, g'o'zaning bo'yi 85,6 sm., hosil shoxlari 10,7 dona, ko'sak soni 11,2 dona va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 7,3 donani tashkil qilib, nazorat variantiga nisbatan hosil shoxlari 0,5 donaga, ko'saklarining soni 0,8 donaga va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 1,1 donaga ko'p bo'lganligi kuzatilgan bo'lsa bir sentner paxta yetishtirish uchun 58,8 m³/s suv resurslari sarflanib, 37,8 s/ga paxta hosili olishga erishilganligi haqida ilmiy natijalar keltirilgan.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida suvni tejaydigan texnologiyalarni joriy qilishdagi mavjud kamchilik va muammolarni bartaraf etish, mintaqada kuzatilayotgan suv tanqisligining salbiy ta'sirini yumshatish, shuningdek, qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarini yetishtirishda suv resurslaridan yanada samarali foydalanish maqsadida 2022 yilda 230 ming gektar, shu jumladan 160 ming gektar paxta xom ashyosi yetishtiriladigan maydonlarda tomchilatib sug'orish, 28 ming gektar, shu jumladan 25 ming gektar boshqoqli don yetishtiriladigan maydonlarda yomg'irli sug'orish, 2 ming gektar qishloq xo'jaligi ekin maydonlarida diskretli sug'orish tizimlari joriy qilinish, shuningdek, 218 ming gektar ekin maydonlarining lazerli uskuna yordamida tekislanishini tashkil etish rejlashirilgan.

Shuningdek, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 10-iyuldagi PF-6024-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasi suv xo'jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020-2030 yillarga mo'ljallangan kontsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi farmoni tasdiqlangan.

Ushbu kontsepsiyaga asosan so'nggi yillarda yer va suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanish, suv resurslarini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish, suv xo'jaligi obyektlarini modernizatsiya qilish va rivojlantirish bo'yicha izchil islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Tadqiqotning obyekti: Buxoro viloyati Vobkent tumanida joylashgan – Yangikent

Oltin Zamini fermer xo'jaligi yerlari hamda g'ozaning "Buxoro-102" navi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Tadqiqotlar davomida g'ozaning o'sib rivojlanishiga lazerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislanmagan maydoni sug'orishda nazorat 1-variantda meyoridan ortiq sug'orish ishlari olib borilganligi sababli g'ozaning bo'yi 95,1 sm, hosil shoxlari 10,8 dona, ko'saklarining soni 10,2 dona va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 6,2 donani, o'sishi va rivojlanishi nisbatan jadal bo'ldi.

Tajribaning lazerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan maydonda tuproqning sug'orish oldi namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 70-80-65 % bo'lganda, g'ozaning bo'yi 85,6 sm., hosil shoxlari 10,7 dona, ko'sak soni 11,2 dona va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 7,3 donani tashkil qilib, nazorat variantiga nisbatan hosil shoxlari 0,5 donaga, ko'saklarining soni 0,8 donaga va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 1,1 donaga ko'p bo'lganligi kuzatildi.

1-rasm lazerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan maydonda g'ozaning o'sib-rivojlanishi bo'yicha fenologik tuzatuvlar olib boorish jarayoni

Kuzatuvlar davomida 1 sentner paxta hosili yetishtirish uchun eng ko'p miqdorda sarflangan suv resurslari tadqiqotlarning 1- variantida, ya'ni 150,8 m³/s ga teng bo'di. Ushbu variantda paxta hosildorligi 27,1 s/ga teng bo'ldi. Tajribalarning ikkinchi variantida, ya'ni lazerli bilan tekislangan variantda tuproqning sug'orish oldi namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 70-75-65 % bo'lganda, bir sentner paxta yetishtirish uchun 58,8 m³/s suv resurslari sarflanib, 2-variantimizda 37,8 s/ga paxta hosili olishga erishildi. Bu esa o'z navbatida nazorat variantiga nisbatan 10,7 s/ga ko'p hosil olishga erishildi. Hosil ko'rsatgichlari Vobkent tumani "Yangikent Oltin Zamini" fermer xo'jaligi katta trassa asfalt yo'l bo'yidagi konturda amalga oshirildi.

1-jadval

Lazerli yer tekislangan maydoning g'ozaga hosildorligiga ta'siri.

№	Sug'orish usuli	Qaytariqlar bo'yicha paxta hosili, s/ga			O'rtacha hosil s/ga	Qo'shimcha hosil nazoratga nisbatan ± s/ga	1 s paxta hosiliga ketgan suv sarfi
		I	II	III			
1	Ishlab chiqarish nazorati	29,5	30,4	28,9	29,5	-0,0	192,8 m ³
2	Lazerli yer tekislangan maydon	42,9	42,5	43,1	42,7	+12,6	60,5 m ³

Tadqiqot natijalari, sug'orishning ilmiy asoslangan tizimida amalga oshirilishi «Buxoro-102» g'oz'a navlari parvarishida eng yuqori hosilni ta'minlanishi mavsumda odatdagi beriladigan suv miqdorini iqtisod qilish imkoniyatini yaratdi.

Buxoro viloyatining hududi turli ob-havo, tuproq-sharoiti bilan ajralib turadi, shuni inobatga olib turli tuproq iqlim sharoitlarda tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi, jumladan Vabkent tumani Yangikent QFY hududidagi "Yangikent Oltin Zamini" fermer xo'jaligi dalalarida ham sinovdan o'tkazildi. Paxta hosildorligi ma'lumki, tuproq ball boniteti, strukturasi, o'tmishdosh ekin turi, suv ta'minoti va olib boriladigan agrotexnika tadbirlar majmui turi va sifatiga bevosita bog'liq. Shu sababli "Yangikent Oltin Zamini" fermer xo'jaligida tejamkor sug'orish usuli yuqori samara berdi va hosildorlik gektaridan 20.7 sentrerga oshishi kuzatildi.

Suv taqchilligining salbiy oqibatlarini kamaytirish maqsadida suv tejoychi usullar va texnologiyalarni qo'llash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Hududimizda asosiy maydonlarda g'oz'a an'anaviy usulda ya'ni egat orqali bostirib sug'orilada. An'anaviy usulda sug'orishda suvning bir qismi o'qariqlarda bug'lanishi va tuproqning pastki qismlariga shimilib ketishi natijasida suv behuda sarflanmoqda. Suvning bug'lanishi va shimilishi tufayli gektariga 2.0-2.5 ming/m³ suv bekorga sarf bo'lishi tadqiqotlarda aniqlangan. Bundan tashqari g'oz'a qator orasiga ishlov berishni muddatidan kechikishi ham suvdan foydalanish samaradorligini pasaytiradi. Shu bilan birga qator orasiga ishlov berilgan g'ozaning ildiz tizimi ma'lum darajada shikastlanishi evaziga o'simlikning o'sish va rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Yuqorida bayyon etilgan salbiy holatlarning oldini olish maqsadida g'oz'a va boshqa qator orasiga ishlov beriladigan ekinlarni sug'orishning zamonaviy agrotexnik usullarini ishlab chiqish hamda intensiv usulni fermer va dehqon xo'jaliklari amaliyotiga keng tadbiriq etish dolzarb masalalardan hisoblanadi. Maydonlarni lazerli yer tekislash texnologiyasi sug'orish suviga bo'lgan talabni va barcha xarajatlarni kamaytiruvchi va tuproq unumdorligini oshirish imkonini beruvchi haqiqiy texnologik va texnik yechimdir.

Vobkent tumani "Yangikent Oltin Zamini" fermer xo'jaligi dalalarida o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari ko'rsatishicha, lazerli yer tekislash texnologiyasi orqali sug'orish suvining sarfi 42.8 % tashkil etdi, usuldan foydalanib sug'orishlar amalga oshirilgan holatda qo'shimcha paxta hosili 13.1 s/ga teng bo'ldi.

Resurstejamkor sug'orish texnologiyasida uzun egatlarda tuproqning bir tekis namlanishi, sug'orishdan keyin tuproq namligining bug'lanishining kamayishi, plynka ostiga quyosh nuri tushmasligi tufayli begona o'tlarning nobud bo'lishi, qator orasiga kultivator bilan ishlov berilmasligi sababli tuproqning zichlanmasligi hamda kam me'yordagi sug'orish natijasida tuproqning unumdor qatlamining sifatli namlanishi hisobiga ildiz tizimi jadal rivojlanishi uchun qulay sharoit yaratilishi va hosildorlikni oshishi aniqlandi.

Xulosa: Lezerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan yerlarda go'zani o'sib-rivojlanishi va hosildorligi bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda lazerli yer tekislagich bilan tekislangan maydonda tuproqning sug'orish oldi namligi ChDNS ga nisbatan 70-80-65 % bo'lganda, g'ozaning bo'yi 85,6 sm., hosil shoxlari 10,7 dona, ko'sak soni 11,2 dona va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 7,3 donani tashkil qilib, nazorat variantiga nisbatan hosil shoxlari 0,5 donaga, ko'saklarining soni 0,8 donaga va 1-sentyabrda ochilgan ko'saklar soni 1,1 donaga ko'p bo'lganligi kuzatilgan bo'lsa bir sentner paxta yetishtirish uchun 58,8 m³/s suv resurslari sarflanib, 37,8 s/ga paxta hosili olishga erishildi. Bu esa o'z navbatida nazorat variantiga nisbatan 10,7 s/ga ko'p hosil olishga erishildi.

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